

ADVANCES IN COMPOSITES RESEARCH FOR MARINE STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

With the increasing use of composites in marine structures, and greater emphasis on affordability and reduction in life-cycle costs, it is necessary to utilize physically based models for the prediction of performance and reliability of these structures, instead of empirically based criteria along with 'large' factors of safety. The marine environment is very hostile, and the designer of marine structures has to account for: (i) the presence of sea water and moisture, (ii) exposure to widely varying temperatures, (iii) varying loading due to waves, slamming, and other factors, and (iv) three-dimensional states of stress. In addition, Naval structures are required to withstand highly dynamic loading during combat situations due to weapons impact, or to air or underwater explosions. The major requirements governing the design of future Naval structures include: Affordability, Survivability, Reliability, Durability, and Structural Integrity.

This presentation describes the research program on "Composites for Marine Structures" of the Office of Naval Research, Ship Structures and Systems S&T Division, which was established to provide the scientific basis for the effective design of affordable Naval structures utilizing composites and composite sandwich construction. An overview will be presented, with a discussion of the program objectives, research issues, recent research accomplishments, and future directions. This program utilizes a combination of advanced experimental techniques, modern theories, and detailed computations, in order to elucidate physical and mechanical phenomena associated with the behavior of composite materials and structures in the marine environment. The ultimate objective is the establishment of physically based theories and models for the thermo-mechanical response, damage initiation, damage progression, and ultimate failure of composites, subjected to complex three-dimensional time-dependent loading. Investigations span a wide range of scales, from models for degradation at the fiber-matrix interface due to moisture, to the buckling of thick composite cylindrical shells due to hydrostatic pressure.

A number of recent research accomplishments will be highlighted, including: coupling between sea water absorption and mechanical fatigue; evolution of fiber/ply waviness in thick composites; degradation of stiffness and strength due to waviness; nondestructive evaluation techniques for the detection and assessment of waviness; compression failure models (microbuckling, kink band formation, etc.); effect of hydrostatic pressure on constitutive behavior; delamination growth under fatigue loading; low velocity impact damage; dynamic constitutive behavior and strain rate effects; dynamic failure modes; failure mode transitions due to confinement; failure modes in sandwich structures; impact damage in sandwich structures; failure of joints in composites; and process models for RTM composites.

The use of innovative experimental techniques for the real-time assessment of damage and failure in composites will also be discussed. For example, the optical Coherent Gradient Sensor technique for full deformation field assessment, coupled with high speed photography (two million frames per second), has provided the most detailed descriptions of highly dynamic failure events. Dynamic delaminations have been investigated in laminated composites, and delamination speeds have been estimated. Dynamic crack initiation toughness for Mode-I crack propagation in a unidirectional composite has been measured as a function of loading rates. Recent investigations into crack propagation under Mode-II loading in unidirectional composite materials have shown the existence of shock fronts, and propagation speeds of the order of 9000 meters per second have been measured. This interesting phenomenon will be discussed and comparisons will be made with dynamic failure in metals. Current and planned composite Naval structures and structural components will also be discussed, including an advanced enclosed mast structure, composite hulls for mine-hunters, composite topside structures, a composite deckhouse, and a composite material transporter.